

Predominance of information

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The issues leading the media agendas, locally and globally, in the last month are related to sport, violence, and climate. Although it is clear that events demand that what affects communities be shown, there is a homogenization of narratives that centralize reports on a few perspectives and protagonists.

Large shares of diversity are ignored by streaming providers and broadcasters who decide what, how and when to show events, and if necessary standardize formats.

It would seem that football and cycling, two wars and hurricanes are the most important things happening today. Despite the fact that these phenomena impact countries and can condition world politics, there are millions of other realities that remain hidden from public opinion and the right to freedom of expression is interrupted.

Conflicts arising from environmental mismanagement, the urgency to preserve water sources, the need to combat illicit drug use, changes in engine production, the regulation of disinformation and artificial intelligence, inclusive education, food sovereignty or the political economy of citizenship, among other issues, are marginalized.

Pedagogical processes need to be developed through the media to draw attention to changing agendas. One option is to reduce the spectacle or "faradisation" of the news to open up radio, TV and online media studios to the people, so that it is the citizens who are on the sets to engage in dialogue in search of peace, justice and sustainable development.